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Intelligent System Concept of Integrated Education History in Single Identity Number Using Grid-Based Model (GBM)

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Abstract – The growing number of educated individuals in Indonesia is the reason behind the significance of research on intelligent system development, which can yield a new model to assess the accuracy of data on educated individuals in Indonesia. This will allow all education data to be integrated with the Single Identity Number, facilitating the retrieval of information on educated individuals such as elementary graduates, junior high school graduates, high school graduates, young experts, associate experts, bachelors, masters, and doctors. Naturally, the Grid-Based Model (GBM) is the ideal role model to use in order to maximize accuracy in the construction of this intelligent system when measuring data accuracy for graduates of formal education. In order to make it simpler to determine research outcomes, while developing an intelligent system in research employing the Paradigm Model of Verification, Evaluation, Restructuring, Data Integration (VERDI Model). It is anticipated that this research will result in an intelligent system that achieves ideal data accuracy within the range of 65% to 100%. The achievement of highly optimal accuracy can have a beneficial effect on the data integration of Indonesian graduates in education. Unified Modeling Language (UML), an object-oriented design tool, will be used for the design modeling of this intelligent system's development, whereas flowcharts are used for the design of the study's algorithm model.

Keywords: Education, GBM, UML, Single Identity Number, Algorithm Model Design, and Data Accuracy.

I. INTRODUCTION

As Indonesia's population grows, it is necessary to integrate data on education graduates of each students in order to optimize the management of occupation data and the background of each individual students in Indonesia. This way, when an integrated intelligent system is developed, it should be able to accurately retrieve historical data on education graduates of all Indonesian studentss.

To establish an intelligent system that can integrate the history of graduates completed by students with reference to the Single Identity Number, in order to create a data management system for students education graduates in Indonesia, it is deemed necessary. This will facilitate the control of a students educational background. It is therefore envisaged that this intelligent system[1][2], which unifies an individual's educational background with a unique identity number, will enable the curation of a students educational history.

An innovation in enabling the control of the background of education graduates of every students in Indonesia is the creation of an integrated intelligent system for education graduates in a single identity number.

An artificial intelligence program or system that combines a knowledge base and an inference engine is known as an intelligent system[3][4]. It is a component of a high-level programming language or high-level specialized software[5][6]

II. REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE AND METHODS

A. Computerized Intelligence

Intelligent Automation and Expert Systems One area of computer science that makes use of computers to enable intelligent behavior akin to that of humans is artificial intelligence[2][7][8]. The field of computer science creates hardware and software that can mimic human behavior[9]

B. Unified Modeling Language, or UML

Using the Unified Modelling Language (UML) technique, object-oriented systems can be designed visually[6][10]. The Object Management Group first developed UML, releasing version 1.0 in January 1997[8][11]

The Unified Modeling Language (UML), also referred to as the standard language for writing software blueprints, is a standard language for visualizing, designing, and documenting systems[12].

It is anticipated that the Unified Modeling Language (UML) will make software engineering easier and that it will accurately, fully, and efficiently satisfy all user needs. Scalability, resilience, security, and other aspects are included in this[11].

One kind of UML (Unified Modelling Language) diagram that shows the relationships between actors and systems is the use case diagram. A use case can explain the kind of communication that takes place between the system and its user. The use case is a simple concept to understand. As seen in Use Case[11][13], the first stage of modeling necessitates the creation of a diagram that can explain the actions of actors with actions within the system.

An activity diagram, also known as an activity diagram in Indonesian, is a type of diagram that can be used to represent different system processes. similar to a vertical sequence representing the steps involved in operating a system[14]. One type of UML diagram used in the creation of a use case is the activity diagram[15][13].

An object's interaction based on a time sequence is depicted in a sequence diagram. The Use Case diagram[15][13], states that sequence can be used to describe the steps that need to be completed in order to produce something.

A class diagram, also known as a package diagram, is a diagram that is used to show classes as packages in order to satisfy a need for packages that will be used in the future[15].

C. Grid-Based Models

Using a two-dimensional framework to align and arrange design elements is known as a grid system[16]. A grid system, on the other hand, is a structure made up of a number of vertical and horizontal lines that is used in web design to arrange content. For layouts, particularly responsive layouts, Bootstrap's grid system is utilized. A set of measurements known as a grid system is useful in design[17][18]

An arrangement system for layouts is called a grid. Print media, like books, magazines, or posters, and screen media, like websites, applications, or other user interfaces, can both use layouts. There are a lot of grid systems that use squares, squares, and rectangles. Instead of using layout to accomplish goals, design elements can be put inside these boxes[17][19].

A grid system is a framework made up of several horizontal and vertical lines that cross one another[18][20][21]. It is utilized to arrange the information in[18].

C. Verification, Evaluation, Restructuring, and Data Integration Research Paradigm (VERDI Model)

The Data Integration Development Model is an intelligent system design that has the ability to integrate information about

each students's educational background and degree recipients[22][23].

In the hopes that it would make it simpler to control or ascertain a students's educational background, the researcher developed a new method for integrating data on education graduates of each individual students who has a history of education and has been declared graduated in completing the education taken. This method, known as the Model of Integration of Education Graduate data[24][25], was thought through for this study. Therefore, in order to integrate the background data of education graduates of each individual students[26], the research uses the Paradigm Model of Verification, Evaluation, Restructuring, Data Integration (VERDI Model) in this study. The Data Integration Development Model developed with the VERDI Paradigm Model is shown in Fig. 1 below:

Fig. 1: VERDI Model (Research Paradigm)

The Research Paradigm Model Fig..1 was further explained by the researcher.

- Researchers engage in **System Requirement Analysis** as a means of identifying issues and creating sustainable solutions.
- **Intelligent Application Design** is a type of intelligent application system design that makes it easier to verify and assess information combined into a single identity number, including residence, education, and birthdate.
- **Verification and Validation** is a system test that demonstrates that data collection methods satisfy all specifications established at specific development stages in order to minimize errors when data input in various

research methods is performed. However, validation is the process of confirming through unbiased, scientific testing that these requirements are met.

- **Evaluation and Testing** is a procedure to gauge the degree to which a students's educational attainment is certain, whereas evaluation is a methodical process to ascertain or make decisions regarding the degree to which the goals of educational achievement are owned by a students in Indonesia.
- **Restructuring and Installation** is the process of setting up a system with data integrated with an intelligent system to be applied and used, whereas restructuring is the management of data management by concentrating on a single identity of all attributes of an individual students.
- **Data integration and Implementation** is an intelligent system that uses a population data set that refers to a single master number to integrate applications for both centralization and decentralization. As an intelligent system is being implemented, care must be taken to ensure that conventional systems are converted into integrated intelligent systems.

D. Integrated System ConFig.uration for the Grid-Based Model (GBM)

The researcher provides an overview of the grid-based model integrated system (GBM) conFig.uration in this section. The GBM is conFig.d on the master data server as the central integration of data from the single identity of individual studentss regarding all histories about a person's biodata, allowing for the methodical entry of educational background data into resident population data. Fig. 2 below shows some of the integrated data, which include information on graduates of elementary, junior, and senior high schools as well as information on young experts, associate experts, bachelor's, master's, and doctoral degrees.

Fig. 2: ConFig.uration for Data Integration

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION (OUTCOMES AND TALK)

A. Concepts of data integration flow

In order to integrate data through a grid-based system and structure the process to achieve data accuracy optimization, the researcher explains the flow model of the data integration system algorithm in this section. In relation to that, the data integration flow is shown in Fig. 3 below:

Fig. 3: Concepts of data integration flow

Rule 1

If Education Single ID 1, Name A and Grid Single ID 1, Name "A" are both true, then

If Education Single ID 0 and Grid Single ID 1, Name "A" and B, respectively, then False

Rule 2

True if Title or Degree Single ID 1, Name A, and Grid Single ID 1, Name "A" are present.

If Title or Degree Single ID 0 and Grid Single ID 1, Name "A" are present, then False.

B. Variable Instrument for Research Attribute

To facilitate the identification of the data that will be incorporated into the intelligent system, the researcher explains the Research Attribute Variable Instrument in this section. This data is displayed in Table I.

Table I: Variable Instruments for Research Attribute

Single Identity	Student Name	ID Code of School Identity (Elementary School, Junior High School, Vocation High School)	ID Code of Higher Education or University Identity : Vocational : (D1/D2/D3/D4) Academic Degree: (S1/S2/S3)
Single Student Identity	Student Name	Graduate School Background	Graduate School Background

In Table I. Research Attribute Variable Instruments Overview Instrument

- The first column : Number for Student Single Identity
- The second column : Name of Student
- The third column: Lists the ID codes for each type of school (elementary, junior high, and high school).
- Fourth Column: University Identity or ID Code for Postsecondary Education (Academic and Vocational)

Table II.a: Processed Students Data Set Samples by Grade Level: Elementary, High School, and Vocational

Single ID	Student Name	Elementary School :	Junior High School :	High School and Vocational High School:
5.31003E+15	Antonius Rio	SD INPRES - 50303693	SMPN - 50303365	SMAS - 50303445
531013670799001	Bergita Bian	SD INPRES - 50303478	SMPN - 10495468	SMAN - 50303316.
531607651189003	Karolina Tato	Tidak ada	SMPN - 50309378	SMAK- 50302950
317205080599001	AHMAD SUBHAN	MIS - 60706544	SMPN - 20101529	SMKN - 20107439
3327091210830014	Sukamto	Tidak ada	Tidak ada	Tidak ada
18564002	Muhamad Ramadani	SDN - 20105377	SMPN - 20100276	SMAS - 20103190
5310052707970013	Sulastio Bransdma Jelemat	SDK - 50303300.	SMPS - 50303356	SMAK - 50303418
317204430380008	Rosdiana	SDN - 20100586	SMPN - 20100773	SMAN - 20100795
122409230700001	Berkat Julmin Waruwu	Tidak ada	Tidak ada	Tidak ada
317506620194003	ADE SILVIA	SDN - 20104112	SMPN - 20103589	SMAN- 20103299.
531003110797004	Benediktus Randi	SD INPRES - 50303693	SMPN - 50308505	SMAS - 50303445
530819430696002	YUNITA SARI ADIPAPA	SD INPRES - 50302743	SMPK - 50302658	Tidak ada
320405030693002	Nurwalid Akhri Hidayat	SDN - 20207601	SMPN - 20219383	SMAN - 20219249
530208540998002	Lebrati kabnani	SD INPRES - 50300510	SMPK - 50307193	SMKS - 50308481
317105200401002	Abimanyu Yuniar Rasyid Putro	SDN - 20100377	SMPN - 20100228	SMKN - 20100168
3275086611990012	Farah Fadhilah	SDN - 20222887	SMPN - 20103621	SMKS - 20103725
317103250197005	Ihramsyah	SDN - 20104676	SMPN - 20100240	SMKM - 20100115
351009100598004	Mahendra Cahyanto	SDN - 20108643	SMPM - 20525536	SMKN - 20525627.
321103571292001	Sri Purwanti	SDN - 20251841	SMPN - 20234056	SMAN - 20208391
531012650200006	Scolastika Sabina Diah Mitak	SD INPRES - 50303476	SMPK - 50303352	SMAN - 50303429
17570016	Muhamad Adrian Nurcholis	SDN - 20100495	SMPN - 20100232	SMKS - 20103547

Fig. 4: Data set processing table Research tools bearing the academic institution's name

Fig. 5: Research instruments with educational institution code in a table processed data set

Table II.b: A Sample of Students Data Sets Analyzed according to Academic and Vocational College

Single ID	Students Name	Vocational Diploma of Collage	Academic Degree of University
5.31003E+15	Antonius Rio	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 033080
5310136707990001	Bergita Bian	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 033080
5316076511890003	Karolina Tato	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 033080
3172050805990001	AHMAD SUBHAN	Associate Expert - 033080	Bachelor - 033080
3327091210830014	Sukamto	Associate Expert - 21413	Bachelor - 033080
18564002	Muhamad Ramadani	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 033080
5310052707970013	Sulastio Bransdma Jelemat	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 033080
3172044303800008	Rosdiana	Associate Expert - 001003	Bachelor - 033080
1224092307000001	Berkat Julmin Waruwu	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 031023
3175066201940003	ADE SILVIA	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 033080
5310031107970004	Benediktus Randi	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 033080
5308194306960002	YUNITA SARI ADIPAPA	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 033080
3204050306930002	Nurwalid Akhri Hidayat	Associate Expert - 041057	Bachelor - 033080
5302085409980002	Lebrati kabnani	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 033080
3171052004010002	Abimanyu Yuniar Rasyid Putro	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 033080
3275086611990012	Farah Fadhilah	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 031023
3171032501970005	Ihramsyah	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 033080
3510091005980004	Mahendra Cahyanto	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 033080
3211035712920001	Sri Purwanti	Associate Expert - 031065	Bachelor - 033080
5310126502000006	Scolastika Sabina Diah Mitak	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 033080
17570016	Muhamad Adrian Nurcholis	Tidak ada	Bachelor - 033080

Table III: Verification Results Summation Ratio and Students Data Set Assessment Using Educational Background

Education Level	Education Summation Ratio
SDN – State Elementary School	11
SDI – State Elementary School	6
MIS – Non-state Elementary School	1
SMPN – State Junior High School	13
SMPS – Non-state Junior High School	1
SMPK – Non-state Junior High School	3
SMPM – Non-state Junior High School	1
SMAN - State High School	6
SMKN – State Vocational High School	3
SMKM – Non-state Vocational High School	1
SMKS – Non-state Vocational High School	3
SMAS – Non-state High School	3
SMAK – Non-state High School	2
Vocational Diploma (D3) - Associate Expert	5
Academic Degree (S1) - Bachelor	21

Fig. 6: Graph of Verification Results Summation and Students Data Set Evaluation by Education Level

Fig. 7: A graph showing the evaluation of the students data set by primary school level and the summation ratio of the verification results

Fig. 8: Summation Ratio of Verification and Evaluation Outcomes for Students Data Sets by Junior High School Level

Fig. 9: Graph of Verification Results Summation Ratio and Students Data Set Evaluation by High School and Vocational Level

Fig. 10: Graph of Total Verification Outcomes and Students Data Set Assessment by Academic and Vocational Level

IV. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that, in order to facilitate the Government of the Republic of Indonesia's efforts to ascertain the educational background of every Indonesian students, an integrated intelligent system is required to incorporate the history data of each individual

students's education graduate into the Single Identity Number of Population. The findings highlight the significance of a grid-based model (GBM)-based intelligent system. The results of the verification and evaluation of the research instrument sample data processing yield a Summation Ratio based on education level, with Elementary Schools having as many as 18 residents, Junior High Schools having as many as 18, Senior High Schools having as many as 11, Vocational High Schools having as many as 7, Vocational College (Associate Experts) having as many as 5, and Academic Universities (Bachelor) having as many as 21. This is in line with the increasing development of artificial intelligence technology to integrate all data sets through a single population identity number.

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